

Implementation of Kanban

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1. Principle

Kanban (かんばん(看板)) is a scheduling system for lean and just-in-time (JIT) production. Kanban is a system to control the logistical chain from a production point of view. Kanban was developed by Taiichi Ohno, at Toyota, to find a system to improve and maintain a high level of production. Kanban is one method through which JIT is achieved.

Kanban became an effective tool in support of running a production system as a whole, and it proved to be an excellent way for promoting improvement. Problem areas were highlighted by reducing the number of kanban in circulation.

1.1 History

- Developed by Toyota in year 1950s. (Kanban is a Japanese word & means Label)

For the following reasons:

1. Overproduction
2. Insufficient Productivity – Avoiding waste
3. Lack of raw material & space
4. Complexity of central production control

- Companywide implementation in Toyota in late 1960s
- In Europe the Kanban is used in early 1990s
- In India the Kanban is used in early 1990s

1.2 Purpose

Kanban causes a pulling of material from a downstream position to an upstream position within the production process. This means, the upstream position only supplies the downstream position with parts if they demand them. The demand of parts will be done by the Kanban (jap. for label). The Kanban-card contains all necessary information for the material-flow. Kanban-material buffers between producer and consumer are limited upwards. This cap of the coverage will be achieved by a limited number of Kanban-cards, which are circulating between up- and downstream position. Therefore the usage of a Kanban system counteracts the main type of waste “overproduction”.

Kanban aligns inventory levels with actual consumption; a signal is sent to produce and deliver a new shipment when material is consumed. These signals are tracked through the replenishment cycle, bringing visibility to both the supplier and the buyer.

Kanban uses the rate of demand to control the rate of production, passing demand from the end customer up through the chain of customer-store processes.

1.3 Currently there exist four different Kanban-methods:

- Production Kanban
- Stock transfer Kanban (from central to decentral stock and also from decentral to decentral stock)
- Supplier Kanban with external supplier's
- **NEW:** Supplier Kanban with the CONSUMER's or **CONSUMER-supply with Kanban** (Topic of this manual)

1.3.1 Supply with Kanban (Supplier-Kanban)

Procedure	Bin Status
The consumer withdraws parts out of a Kanban bin.	6111
As soon as the parts are completely consumed, the Kanban-Card should be scanned EMPTY and destroyed afterwards.	6111
Caused by this EMPTY-Scan a new Kanban-replenishment-purchase order (Kanban-PO) for the quantity of this bin will be created.	6111
A cyclic job (ZMZKAN09) at the consumer checks the data of all Kanban-PO's. If all data are OK the status of the Kanban bin will be set to PROCESS "Container in process" and the EOI order transfer will be started.	6111
The supplier get's a new Sales order created by EOI. This Sales-order obtains the delivery priority " 88 " which identifies them as special Kanban Sales orders (Kanban SO).	6111
A cyclic job at Supplier checks the availability in the Supplier-Kanban stock and if the material is available, the Kanban-SO will be released and confirmed automatically.	6111
Another cyclic job creates the delivery note and prints the Kanban-Card directly in -shipment dept. at Supplier automatically.	6111
After packing and labeling the goods, the "goods issue" will be posted in Supplier and the bin status at the consumer will be set to TRANSP "Container in transport". The goods will be transported to the Consumer.	6111
After arriving at the Consumer the goods will be transported to its shelf in Consumer-production and the worker does the FULL-Scan on the attached Kanban-Card. MIGO will be done in the background automatically.	6111

2 Requirements

The following requirements are necessary for the conversion of a material-number at CONSUMER-Kanban. Each of them will be described in detail:

- Appropriate material-numbers.
- Supermarket-shelves which comply with the standard.
- Existing Kanban-Terminals with SAP-access.
- Material-number must be already set up in the Kanban-stock of the supplier.

2.1 Material-Numbers

An appropriate material-number for CONSUMER-Kanban should have a consumption of minimum the quantity of one Kanban-bin per month or more. This consumption has to be regular, which means min. once a month.

The calculation of the number of bins, considering consumption, filling-quantity, replacement-time and safety-time, should be done with this suggested Excel-sheet.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Mat no.	material description	Consumption last 3 month	consumption per day	Repl. lead time RLT [workdays]	bin (type)	quantity per bin	safety time ST [workdays]	quantity of KANBANS	pack. unit	
2	71021400 Housing T14_M48+air +1xM20 plug-b/WA	750	11,90	7	supplier carton	16	4,9	9,854167	10	
3			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
4			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
5			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
6			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
7			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
8			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
9			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
10			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
11			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
12			0,00					#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	

In this sheet can be filled in all material-numbers with their shorttext, material –type and consumptions. Afterwards the following fields have to be filled in for the calculation of the number of bins:

- Replacement time or replenishment lead time (RLT = time between Empty- and full-scan)
- Kanban-bin
- Quantity per bin
- Safety time (min. half RLT)

On the basis of this data, the needed number of bins/cards which have to be circulated, will be calculated automatically (Column “Cards rounded“). The calculation will be done with the following formula:

$$\text{Number of Kanban cards} = \frac{(\emptyset \text{ Consumption/WD} \times \text{RLT}) + (\text{ST} \times \emptyset \text{ Consumption/WD})}{\text{Quantity/bin}} + 1$$

RLT: Replacement time or replenishment lead time in WDs (time between Empty- and full-scan)

ST: Safety time in WDs

WD: Workday

- 1) Container from which currently the parts will be withdrawn (Container in use!)

2.2 Supermarket

A Kanban-storage (also called Supermarket-shelve) should be built, as in **two pager No. HA 9** explaine.

SMART+Q – two pager No. 9 Supermarket (decentralised stock)	
Description A supermarket as an intermediate storage location close to production is reasonable if not all required material can be stocked directly at the workplace. Decentralized warehouses are often known as supermarkets, because they have the same properties as shelves in a retail shop, as e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ large variety of parts ▪ short range of coverage ▪ Items are replaced immediately after the customer has taken one 	
Requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ adequate space ▪ meaningful arranged parts in the warehouse, clearly labelled 	
Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ low level of stocked assets ▪ Increase of transparency ▪ separation of value addition and logistics 	Tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ See work instructions “Marking of shelves” TLL 0094
Tip <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The parts should be arranged according to the appropriate work sequence and frequency of use. ▪ Always try to store the material directly at your workplace. Only use a supermarket system if the quantity of part numbers is too high. 	
<div style="text-align: right;"> <p>storage in the workplace</p> <p>Storage in the work system delivered from outside. The worker receives the parts directly at his workplace.</p> </div>	
<small>Creator: TLP / rtk, state: 20.10.2008</small>	

2.3. Kanban-Terminal

For an efficient handling of the Kanban-process a “Kanban-terminal“ in close proximity to the Kanban-storage is important. This terminal consists of a computer with SAP-access, a large screen (min. 19 inches diagonal) and a wireless barcode-scanner. This “Kanban-terminal“ should meet two requirements. On the one hand, there should be done the “Empty- and the Full-scans“ of the Kanban-cards from the assigned Kanban-storage, on the other hand, it serves the purpose of visualization of all the Kanban controlcycles of this Kanban-storage (Kanban-board e.g. in order of their urgency).

3. Setup

3.1. Supply area

A supply area in SAP is always allocated to a storage location and specifies where Kanban-material must be delivered. A supply area is always a subarea of one decentral stock area.

A supply area is defined in the Kanban-Customizing of SAP and allocated to the following objects:

- One plant
- One storage location
- Person in charge or Responsible (normally the MRP-controller in SAP)

The posting of any material movements will be done on the allocated storage location. Multiple supply areas can be created in one storage location, but one supply area can't be allocated to different storage locations.

If one material is used in different supply areas which are allocated to the same storage location, the view of the stock overview (MMBE) shows always a total sum of all different supply areas.

As a matter of principal, supply areas should be centrally administrated (by the Kanban-experts)

3.1.1. Creation of supply areas in SAP with PK05

PK05

Select plant and click ENTER

Click "New Entries"

Fill in the necessary data.

 Save the new supply area.

3.1.2. Change

PK05

Double click the row which should be changed. Then do the changes and

 Save changes.

3.1.3. Delete

PK05

Mark/highlight the row which should be deleted. Then click "delete" and

 Save changes.

Supply areas can only be deleted if there are nomore any controlcycles allocated to this supply area.

→ Delete controlcycles first.

3.2.Control cycle

3.2.1. Creation of control cycle (PKMC)

CONSUMER-Supply with Kanban (CONSUMER Supplier-Kanban)

Change Material 71028488 (Semifinished product)

Material: 71028488 | Electronics CIDBAR_57HT_SIL_Tst2.10.40
 Plant: 1500 | Address+Hauser (USA)
 Stor. Loc.: 6001 | CERABAR

BOM explosion/dependent requirements
 Selection method: 2 | Component scrap (%):
 Individual coil: | Requirements group:
 Version indicator: | ProdVersions: | MRP dep. requirements:

Discontinued parts
 Discontin. ind.: | Eff-out: | Follow-up mail:

Repetitive manufacturing / assembly / deployment strategy
 Repetitive mfg: | REM profile: | Action control:
 Fair share rule: | Push distribution: | Deployment horizon:

Average plant stock: | Material memo: | Material memo exists:

Storage location MRP
 SLoc MRP indicator: | Spec. proc. type: | SLoc:
 Reorder point: | Replenishment qty:
 Special Memo:
 Iss Loc.:

- **Stor. Loc. MRP indicator “1”** in MM02 / MRP4 for the related storage location must be set before starting the creation, otherwise a new controlcycle can’t be created. After creation of the controlcycle this field **must be deleted** again!

Control Cycle Maintenance: Display

Selection
 Plant: 1500
 Supply Area: 6005A
 Responsible:
 Contr. cycle no.:

Buttons: Detailed Selection

Start **PKMC** and fill in “Plant” and “Supply area” then press the button to change from “Display” to “Change” mode.

In “Change” - mode there’s a button to create a new controlcycle.

Control Cycle Maintenance: Change

Selection
 Plant: 1500
 Supply Area: 6005A
 Responsible:

Buttons: Create Control Cycle

Create Control Cycle

Control Cycle Category
 Classic KANBAN
 Event-driven KANBAN

Material: 52001500
 Plant: 1500
 Supply Area: 6005A

Buttons: Cancel

Choose “Classic KANBAN” and fill in the material number and press the ENTER button.

Fill in the necessary information: **No. of Kanbans, Quantity per bin** and choose a **container part-no** (Only used for printing the container description onto the Kanban-Card)

Kanban Maintenance

Control Cycle 0
 Material: 52001500
 Plug M20x1.5 PBT-GF-FR
 Plant: 1500 | Address+Hauser (USA)
 Supply Area: 6005A | Housing Kanban
 Storing Pos.:

Kanbans
 No. of kanbans: 2 | Maximum empty:
 Kanban quantity: 500 | PC | No. Load Carrier:
 Container: 71083807

Replenishment Strategy: In-house prod. | 1004
 Ext. procurement |
 Stock transfer |

The storing position should only be used if there’s more than one supply area on one storage location. Otherwise this information has to be maintained in material master.

For “CONSUMER-supply with Kanban” the only allowed strategy is “1004”. Then hit **ENTER**

Kanban Maintenance

Control Cycle 5.317
 Material: 52001500
 Plug M20x1.5 PBT-GF-FR
 Plant: 1500 | Address+Hauser (USA)
 Supply Area: 6005A | Housing Kanban
 Storing Pos.:

Kanbans
 No. of kanbans: 2 | Maximum empty:
 Kanban quantity: 500 | PC | No. Load Carrier: 1
 Container: 71083807
 Carton "B5"

External Procurement: External procurement | 1004
 Purchasing Org.: 1500
 Vendor: 5
 Agreement:

Fill in the necessary information: **Purchasing Org. and Vendor-no.**

The field Agreement isn’t necessary for strategy 1004!

Change to tab “Flow control” and fill in the status sequence “KAN6”, the only allowed sequence for “CONSUMER-supply with Kanban”

 Save new controlcycle and remove **Stor. Loc. MRP indicator “1”** in MM02 / MRP4.

Hint: Use whenever possible, an already existing controlcycle as a “copy from” template.

3.2.2. Creation with template (PKMC)

- **Stor. Loc. MRP indicator “1”** in MM02 / MRP4 for the related storage location must be set before starting the creation, otherwise a new controlcycle can’t be created. After creation of the controlcycle this field **must be deleted** again!

Start **PKMC** and fill in the needed selection data e.g. “plant” and “supply area” and start with “F8” or button .

Switch to “change mode” with the button .

Choose the controlcycle which you want to use as a template and press the button “Create with template”

Choose “Classic KANBAN”, fill in the material number and the supply area which you want to create and press “ENTER” .

Now you can follow the same rules than in chapter 3.2.1 Creation of control cycle (PKMC)

 Save new controlcycle and remove **Stor. Loc. MRP indicator “1“** in MM02 / MRP4.

3.2.3. Change controlcycle (PKMC)

.</p>	
)</p> <p>Changing of “Kanban quantity”</p> <p>Changing of the “Container”</p>	
.</p> <p>Each bin can be locked (LkIn) or deleted (DtFg).</p> <p>The locking indicator (LkIn) causes the marking of the bin-id with an “X“, which means, after the next EMPTY-scan this bin will change to status WAIT instead of EMPTY and will no longer be in use. This WAIT is the precondition to delete a bin.</p> <p>The delete indicator (DtFg) can only be set if the bin status is WAIT.</p>	

	<p>After setting the delete indicator (DtFg) the “No. of Kanbans“.will be adjusted automatically.</p>
	<p>Save changes.</p>

3.2.4. Deletion of control cycle (PKMC)

.</p>	
	<p>Before a complete controlcycle can be deleted, all existing bins must have the status WAIT!</p> <p>To achieve that all bins get the status WAIT, the locking indicator must be used (as described in the previous chapter “Change“).</p>
	<p>Press “YES” and save the deletion.</p>

3.3. Material Master Data

CONSUMER-Supply with Kanban (CONSUMER Supplier-Kanban)

Additional Data Org. Levels Check Screen Data Locked fields

Sales Text Purchasing Foreign trade import Purchase Order Text

Material: 71028488 Electronics C/DBAR_S*HT_SIL_Tst*2.10.40
Plant: 1500 Endress+Hauser (USA)

General Data
Base Unit of Measure: PC Piece
Purchasing Group: GK1 Material Group: 646
Plant-sp.matl status: Valid from
Tax ind. f. material: Qual. FreeGoodsDis.
Material freight grp: Autom. PO
 Batch management

Purchasing values
Purchasing value key: F Shipping Instr.
1st Rem./Exped.: 1 days Underdel. Tolerance: 0,0 percent
2nd Reminder/Exped.: 2 days Overdelv. Tolerance: 0,0 percent
3rd Reminder/Exped.: 3 days Min. Del. Qty in %: 0,0 percent
StdValueDelivDateVar: 0 days Unittl Overdelivery Acknowledgment Reqd

Other data / manufacturer data
GR Processing Time: 4 days Post to insp. stock Critical Part
Quota arr. usage: Source list JIT Sched. Indicator
Mfr Part Number: Mfr Part Profile
Manufact.:

View “Purchasing”

Purchasing Group: must have a “K” on the second position. There are 9 different purchasing groups for each CONSUMER available which must be used. E.g. GK1 to GK9 for CONSUMER Greenwood.

Purchasing value key: Must be “F” **no longer needed!**

Goods receipt processing time: Average transport time from SUPPLIER to CONSUMER + internal handling time CONSUMER (Time from Goods receipt to arrival in Kanban stock)

Change Material 71028488 (Semifinished product)

Purchase Order Text MRP 1 MRP 2 MRP 3 MRP 4

Material: 71028488 Electronics C/DBAR_S*HT_SIL_Tst*2.10.40
Plant: 1500 Endress+Hauser (USA)

General Data
Base Unit of Measure: PC Piece
Purchasing Group: GK1 MRP group:
Plant-sp.matl status: ABC Indicator: A
Valid from:

MRP procedure
MRP Type: ZK Attribut for Kanban (PD)
Reorder Point: Planning time fence:
Planning cycle: MRP Controller: GK1

Lot size data
Lot size: FX Fixed order quantity
Minimum Lot Size: Maximum Lot Size:
Fixed lot size: 90 Maximum stock level:
Ordering costs: Storage costs ind.
Assembly scrap (%): Takt time:
Rounding Profile: Rounding value: 90
Unit of Measure Grp:

View “MRP1”

MRP Type: Must be ZK (special type for Kanban-usage)

MRP Controller: The same logic than for the purchasing group (must be identical)

Fixed lot size or min. and max. Lot size: Must be the same than the quantity of the Kanban bin.

Rounding value: If maintained, it must also be the same than the quantity of the Kanban bin.

Reorder Point: Should be empty because it won't work with ZK.

Change Material 71028488 (Semifinished product)

MRP 1 MRP 2 MRP 3 MRP 4 Plant data / stor. 1 Pla...

Material: 71028488 Electronics C/DBAR_S*HT_SIL_Tst*2.10.40
Plant: 1500 Endress+Hauser (USA)

Procurement
Procurement type: X Batch entry:
Special procurement: F Prod. stor. location: 6001
Quota arr. usage: Default supply area:
Backflush: 2 Storage loc. for EP:
JIT delivery sched.: Stock det. grp:
 Co-product Joint production
 Bulk Material

Scheduling
In-house production: days
GR Processing Time: 4 days Planned Deliv. Time: 3 days
SchedMargin key: R Planning calendar:
Net requirements calculation
Safety Stock: Service level (%):
Min safety stock: Coverage profile:
Safety time ind.: 2 Safety time/fact.cov.: 5 days
STime period profile:

View “MRP2”

Planned delivery time: Internal handling time SUPPLIER + Time shift between CONSUMER and SUPPLIER (Normally 3-5 days)
→ Must also be set in the info record.

SchedMargin key: Must be “R”

Safety time indicator: Must be “2” (Safety time for all requirements)

Safety time: Safety time must be the same than used in the Kanban calculation.

Safety stock is not necessary because of the usage of the safety time in the Kanban-calculation which is also a kind of safety stock.

Change Material 71028488 (Semifinished product)

Material: 71028488 | Electronics C/DBAR_S*HT_SIL_Tst*2.10.40
 Plant: 1500 | Endress+Hauser (USA)
 Stor. Loc.: 6001 | CERABAR

Storage location MRP

SLoc MRP indicator: 1 | Spec. proc. type: SLoc
 Reorder point: [] | Replenishment qty: []
 Special Memo: []
 Iss. Loc.: []

View “MRP4” for Kanban storage location

Storage location MRP indicator: For the creation of the Kanban controlcycle this field must be set to “1”, otherwise a controlcycle can’t be created. **After the creation the field must be emptied again.**

All other fields must be empty.

Change Material 71028488 (Semifinished product)

Material: 71028488 | Electronics C/DBAR_S*HT_SIL_Tst*2.10.40
 Plant: 1500 | Endress+Hauser (USA)
 Stor. Loc.: 6001 | CERABAR

General data

Base Unit of Measure: PC | Piece
 Storage Bin: 1C 1D BEX1
 Temp. conditions: []
 Container reqmts: []
 CC phys. inv. ind.: A | CC fixed: []
 Label type: [] | Lab. form: [] | Appr. batch rec. req.: []
 Batch management: []

Shelf life data

Max. storage period: [] | Time unit: []
 Min. Rem. Shelf Life: [] | Total shelf life: []
 Period Ind. for SLED: D | Rounding rule SLED: []
 Storage percentage: []

View “Plant data /stor.1” for Kanban storage location

Storage Bin: This field has to be used to define the coordinate / place where the material physically is stored (shelve position). This information will be printed on the Kanban card.

If there is more than one supply area, this information has to be maintained directly in the controlcycle (field: “storing position”) this overrides the field in material master.

4. Startup

4.1 Preliminaries

- Controlcycle is created
- Material master data are maintained
- Info record and Source list are maintained
- Supermarket (shelve) is set up and the storage compartment is clearly labeled (coordinate as printed on the Kanban card)

For a smooth transition to a Kanban stock it is necessary to repack the existing stock inventory into the new Kanban bins (same quantity and size). If necessary the remaining inventory from Central stock has to be transferred to the Kanban-storage. For the transition into a Kanban stock we have to create so called “Transition Kanban cards” which can’t be done via SAP!

4.2. Creation of transition cards

For the creation of these “transition cards” this little Excel tool (“Manual_KANBAN_card.xlt”) can be used.

1	A	B	C	D	E	F
2	material.#	description	bin description	qty per bin	stor. location	stor. position
2	71028488	Elektronics C/DBAR_S "HT_SIL_Hsr"2.01.03	Carton "BA"	90	G001	1C 1D BEX1
3						
4						
5	List of Kanban-Ids:					
6						
7			1271			
8			1272			
9			1273			
10			1274			
11			1275			
12			1276			
13			1277			
14			1278			
15			1279			
16						
17						
18						
19						
20						
21						
22						
23						
24						
25						
26						
27						

Please fill in the information in line 2 which should appear on the card, then fill in the list of Kanban-IDs of the bins which should get such a initial “transition card”.

You can get the necessary information out of SAP-transaction **PK18** “Evaluation of Kanban controlcycles”

Max. 20 cards can be created in 1 turn.

Then click the Button **Create cards**.

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
2	KANBAN								
3	<i>transition - card</i>								
4	-----								
5	Material: 71028488								
6	Elektronics C/DBAR_S "HT_SIL_Hsr"2.01.03								
7	-----								
8	Quantity: 90 pcs Bin / Container: Carton "BA"								
9	Stor. Loc.: G001 Stor. Position: 1C 1D BEX1								
10	-----								
11	EMPTY								
12	00000001271								
13	[Barcode]								
14	-----								
15	<input type="button" value="Cancel cards"/>								
16									
17									

For each Kanban-ID a separate sheet with a Kanban-card will be created.

These cards can be printed out to label the Kanban bins and the existing barcode can be used for the first EMPTY-scan to start replenishment.

After the printout of the cards the sheets with these cards can be deleted with the button **Cancel cards** on the sheet “data”.

Please note:

If the existing stock is higher than the calculated capacity of the new Kanban controlcycle, the leftover has to be **used up first** (without using Kanban cards).

If the new Kanban controlcycle has more bins than the current stock is covering, the rest of the cards should be

EMPTY scanned, **not at once** but step by step, to avoid a bottleneck situation at the supplier (SUPPLIER).

5. Operating

5.1 Kanban-board

5.1.1 Demand source overview

The “Demand source overview“ will be started with the SAP-transaction “PK13N“ or using the Kanban-Cockpit transaction “ZKanban“.

In the initial screen the selection could be done by Supply area, by Responsible for Supply area (Each supply area is allocated to a responsible MRP-controller (xKx) see chapter 3.1.1) and also by Supply areas by a storage location. With this selection, all Kanban-parts of the chosen storage location will be listed.

With the field “material“ a single part-number can be selected and all controlcycles of this part-number will be listed.

With “Detailed selection“ more detailed delimitations are possible.

5.1.2 Setup of Kanban-board

Change the bin/Kanban display:

To change the bin/Kanban display use menu “Settings” and choose “Display Kanbans”.

SUPPLIER standard setup:

Bins are horizontally sorted

1. By status (ascending)
2. By last change (ascending)

These adjustments have been proven as reliable to trace back possible troubles.

Don't forget to “Save” () the changes.

Change the display of the columns:

To change the column display use menu “Settings” and choose “Display controlcycles”.

Use the button “Field selection” to replace the fields which should be displayed.

There has been programmed a special field to display the urgency of the controlcycles. This field is named “User-exit2”.

This urgency is defined as a ratio of “total number of bins” divided by the “number of empty bins”. (e.g. total are 11 bins and 6 bins are empty, so the ratio is 1.83)

The most urgent ratio is 1.0, which means all bins are empty.

This field can be used to sort the controlcycles by urgency.

The fields will be sorted in order of the “priority“ which is defined for each field.

Example (mostly used in SUPPLIER-Production):

Priority 1: User-exit2 (Urgency)

Priority 2: Supply area

Priority 3: Part-number

Don’t forget to “Save” (Save User Data) the changes.

5.2 Kanban-correction

If there goes something wrong during the status change of a Kanban-bin (e.g. The PO could not be created because this material number is blocked from another user) the bin color changes to “white with a red border” **15751** which signs a Kanban bin as “incorrect”.

With the “Kanban-correction“ these **faulty** or **incorrect** bins can be corrected. Also inadvertently done status changes can be undo.

Right click on the bin which should be corrected and then choose “Kanban-correction“

Doubleclick the line, of the bin, which should be corrected. Status “9“ stands for “**Container incorrect**“. To reverse another status change, choose the line to correct and doubleclick it.

Then the correction window appears underneath

To repeat an unsuccessful status change click the button “**Kanban-correction**“. To set a specific status, choose the status in the field “Kanban-status“ and click the button “**Status/qty**“.

To undo a status change, only the button “**Reverse**“ must be clicked. All background activities will be cancelled and the previous status will be set again.

After leaving the Kanban-correction all changes are saved automatically.

Please note:

This Kanban-correction can only be done by the Kanban-experts with special authorities.

If a Kanban status “PROCSS” has to be undo, SUPPLIER has to be informed because status PROCSS means: purchase order in CONSUMER and also Sales order in SUPPLIER is created. The PO will be deleted automatically but not the SO. SO SUPPLIER has to cancel the corresponding SO manually!

5.3 Peaks in demands (project demands)

A fundamental rule for any known future peak in demands caused by a big customer order (project) is an **intensiv communication** between consumer (CONSUMER) and supplier (SUPPLIER). As soon as SUPPLIER knows about these additional demands, they can take the necessary measures, together with the CONSUMER,

to fulfill them. So the sooner SUPPLIER knows, the better it is. There are different possibilities what to do. Each of them will be described in detail:

- Increasing the number of bins
- Event-driven Kanbans
- Creating additional PO's manually besides the controlcycle

5.3.1 Increasing the number of bins

The first possibility is, to create additional bins in the affected controlcycle and then scan them empty. Afterwards these additional bins must be locked (see chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**), to avoid a repeated Empty-scanning. If a locked bin will be empty-scanned, the status changes to WAIT and the bin could be deleted again (see chapter 3.2.4).

Please note: This can all only be done if SUPPLIER has enough stock for these additional demands and has agreed to this procedure!

5.3.2 Event-driven Kanban

If there are part-numbers which there's more frequently the need of additional bins it would be worthwhile to create so called "Event-driven Kanban controlcycles". This kind of controlcycle allows adding very easy additional bins which will be filled only once and after the second empty scan they vanish again.

Event-driven controlcycle don't have any bins. If there's an additional demand, there can be activated any number of bins which will be used only once, to cover these additional demands.

Event-driven Kanban

PKMC:

It is necessary to create an own supply area for each storage location for these "special" controlcycles.

Please choose "Event-driven Kanban" after starting PKMC. Please see chapter 3.2.1 "Creation of controlcycle" for more information how to create a new controlcycle.

Event-driven Kanban

Usage:

If you need an additional bin, right click on the controlcycle and choose “Create Kanban”

Click on the button “**Create Kanban**” and an empty scanned bin will be created.

Please note: This also can only be done if **SUPPLIER has enough stock** for these additional demands and **has agreed** to this procedure!

5.3.3 Creating additional PO’s manually

The third possibility is, to create additional PO’s beside the normal CONSUMER-Kanban supply, which will be handled completely separated from this automatic process on both sides. Following steps have to be done:

- A “normal” PO (PO-type **NB**) has to be created manually with the additional quantity. Purchasing group mustn’t be **GK1** to **GK9**, to avoid the creation of a Kanban-Sales order in SUPPLIER.
- Order will be transferred via EOI to SUPPLIER and creates a “normal” SO for CONSUMER-supply.
- SO will be proceeded manually as any other SO for CONSUMER-supply. SUPPLIER takes the necessary measures to fulfill these additional demands.
- Material will be shipped as a normal CONSUMER-supply “without” Kanban-card because there’s no corresponding Kanban-bin on the CONSUMER-side.
- Material must be received, stocked and consumed as a normal CONSUMER-supply material, completely besides the Kanban-stock in the CONSUMER-production.

Please note: This can only be done after **detailed coordination and agreement** about quantities and dates, **between CONSUMER and SUPPLIER.**

5.4 Statistic evaluation

5.4.1 Evaluate Kanbans without status changes

With the program, ZMZKAN08 “Kanban without status change“ Kanbans can be found out, which the last status change has been done before n hours. This means there must have been a problem which prevented any further status change.

KANBAN ohne Statuswechsel

Eigenfertigung
 Fremdfertigung
 Umlagerung

Selektion
 Werk: 0001
 Umlagerung: 0003
 Regelkreisnummer: [] bis []
 Identnummer: [] bis []
 ProdVersorgBereich: 0047a bis []
 Kanbanstatus: 4
 Lagernummer: 001
 Statuswechsel vor > n-Stunden: 48

Currently we have the restriction that we can't evaluate max. 99 hours delay. That could be probably not enough to use this tool for the CONSUMER-Kanban.

We are working on this issue!

Anyway, this tool can for example be used to check if there are any Kanban's in the CONSUMER which are more than 4 hours on status EMPTY because normally each empty bin of an CONSUMER-Kanban Controlcycle must be set max. 2 h later to status **PROCSS** "Container in process" by a cyclic job which runs every two hours.

KANBAN ohne Statuswechsel

Regel...	Material	IdentNr.	PrVersBer.	Status	Folge	Werk	Stunden	TB-Nr	TA-Nr	Zähler
34	71021404	156	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1658: 27: 21	800631		1
34	71021404	157	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1658: 27: 20	800630		1
37	71021412	163	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	2010: 27: 19	784329		1
49	52013823	191	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1624: 27: 39	802659		1
50	52013781	192	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1968: 27: 2	786388		1
50	52013781	193	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1818: 27: 8	793438		1
52	52013788	197	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1718: 27: 38	797974		1
52	52013788	198	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	2126: 27: 13	778731		1
57	52013786	211	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1628: 27: 24	802543		1
57	52013786	212	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1626: 27: 26	802655		1
434	012079-1001	1905	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1608: 27: 0	803226		1
434	012079-1001	1911	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1824: 26: 30	792925		1
523	012079-0001	2149	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1780: 25: 47	794852		1
523	012079-0001	2150	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1700: 26: 14	799041		1
2487	71039827	8587	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 23: 10	803449		1
2279	71039858	7925	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	2112: 24: 14	779423	892914	1
2279	71039858	7931	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	2010: 26: 19	784332	898229	1
2279	71039858	7932	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	2006: 27: 4	784436	898345	1
15	52017675	98	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1868: 27: 9	791292	805622	1
54	942421-1603	2711	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1672: 27: 25	800246	915366	1
17	52023679	103	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1672: 27: 31	800253	915456	1
20	52017669	118	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1624: 27: 41	802660	918075	1
24	71021401	133	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 26: 43	803423	918812	1
199	71007304	750	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 26: 13	803450	918813	1
199	71007304	4966	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 26: 11	803452	918814	1
25	71021402	139	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 26: 40	803419	918823	1
24	71021401	121	0047A	4	KAN3	0001	1606: 26: 46	803421	918824	1

The created list shows all Kanbans at which the last status change was longer than n hours ago.

5. 4 Evaluation of Kanbans with MCQ.

There exists another transaction which can be used for different analyses in the Kanban environment. It is called "MCQ."

Kanban Analysis: Selection

SelectVers. User settings Standard drilldown

Characteristics
 Plant: 500 to []
 Supply Area: [] to []
 Storage Location: [] to []
 Material: 71028488 to []
 Responsible: [] to []

Period to analyze
 Date: 01.01.2009 to 05.10.2009

Parameters
 Exception: []

This is a SAP standard transaction with functions which are very similar to MC02. There can be selected plant specific data of controlcycles with different select options.

6. Appendix

6.1 SAP-authorities

SAP-authorization	authorized transactions
Kanban-normal	ZKanban, PK13n PK12n, PKBC
Kanban-extended	All Kanban-transactions except PK05 and PK31
Kanban-extra	All Kanban-transactions

6.2 PK-transactions

Transaction	Function
PKMC	Controlcycle maintenance (Create/Change/View)
PK05	Supply area create, change and view
PK05S	Quick: Supply area create, change and view
PK10	Mass-change Kanban-controlcycles
PK11	Kanban-Plant overview
PK12n	Kanban-board Source view
PK13n	Kanban-board demand view
PKBC	Kanban-impulse (Full-/Empty-scan with Barcode)
PK18	Controlcycle- and Kanban-Evaluation
MCQ.	Kanban-analysis
PK31	Kanban-correction
zKanban	Kanban-Cockpit
ZMZKAN02	Evaluation: Kanban Status-changes
ZMZKAN08	Evaluation: Kanban without Status-changes
ZMZKAN09	Supplier Kanban: Check Master data / Update Purchase order

Transaction	Function
PK01 (obsolete)	Create controlcycle
PK02 (obsolete)	Change controlcycle
PK03 (obsolete)	View controlcycle

6.3 Checklist for the changeover

Changeover to CONSUMER-Kanban		OK
Changings in material master	MM02	
Purchasing Group to *K* USA: GK1 to GK9 China: SK1 to SK9 India: AK1 to AK9	MM02, purchasing	
Goods receipt processing time (Average transport time from SUPPLIER to CONSUMER + internal handling time CONSUMER) USA: "4" workdays China: "7" workdays India: tbd	MM02, purchasing	
MRP-type "ZK"	MM02; MRP 1	
MRP-controller to *K* USA: GK1 to GK9 China: SK1 to SK9 India: AK1 to AK9	MM02; MRP 1	
Fixed lot size or min. and max. Lot size same than bin quantity	MM02; MRP 1	
Rounding value same than bin quantity	MM02; MRP 1	
Remove Reorderpoint	MM02; MRP 1	
Planned delivery time to "3" days (Internal handling time SUPPLIER + Time shift between CONSUMER and SUPPLIER (Normally 3-5 days))	MM02; MRP 2	
SchedMargin key: Must be "R"	MM02; MRP 2	
Safety time indicator "2"	MM02; MRP 2	
Safety time = Safety time from Kanban-calculation	MM02; MRP 2	
Remove safety stock	MM02; MRP 2	

Changeover to CONSUMER-Kanban		OK
Storage location MRP indicator “1” (necessary for Controlcycle-creation)	MM02; MRP 4 / Kanban storage location	
All other fields must be empty!	MM02; MRP 4 / Kanban storage location	
Storage bin: Coordinate / place where the material physically is stored (shelve position). This information will be printed on the Kanban card.	MM02; Plant data /stor.1 for Kanban storage location	
Changings in info record	ME12	
Planned delivery time = same than in material master	Purch. Organization Data 1	
Purchasing group = same than in material master	Purch. Organization Data 1	
Standard quantity = Quantity per bin	Purch. Organization Data 1	
Minimum quantity = Quantity per bin	Purch. Organization Data 1	
Changings in source list	ME01	
Fixed source of supply: Must be checked ✓	Source list	
Usage in MRP: Must be “1”	Source list	
Kanban preparations		
Create supply area	PK05	
Create controlcycle	PKMC	
Empty the storage location MRP indicator (only necessary for Controlcycle-creation)	MM02; MRP 4 / Kanban storage location	
Prepare Kanban shelve / label storage position	Production	
Transfer existing stock to Kanban-shelve and repack into Kanban bins	Production	
Create the transition Kanban cards and label the Kanban bins	Excel tool	

6.4 Containers / bins

Matno.	Short description	Dimensions
71083805	Carton "B3"	300x200x120
71083806	Carton "B4"	400x300x120
71083807	Carton "B5"	400x300x220
71083810	Carton "BA"	600x400x120
71083808	Carton "B6"	600x400x220
71083809	Carton "B7"	600x400x320
71034654	Half pallet	800x600
71034648	Full pallet	1200x800

Conclusion:

This proves that **Kanban** is an effective inventory management system which helps an organisation to achieve the best results in the following key result areas of operation of any plant. JIT is implemented thru the Kanban way :

- 1) Only required / consumed material is getting ordered so unnecessary stocks don't get piled up.
- 2) Vendor is getting sufficient lead time to supply the right material on right time.
- 3) Right quantity & right quality of material is always on the shelf for production.
- 4) Even in unpredictable consumption items the material stocks are reviewed & getting replenished after consumption only.
- 5) Slow moving & non moving consumption material is not getting ordered & hence the stocks are controlled.
- 6) There is no last minute rush happening & despatches to customers are happening in time as per the promise date.
- 7) Kanban helps organisation to improve the **inventory turn** which is a one of the most important key result area for any organisations success.
- 8) Since the right material & right qty is received in the plant, it saves huge storage space which can be utilized for productive work.

Refernces:

- 1) Kanban - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia.
- 2) Various literature on www.google.co.in